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Deadlock-Free and Collision-Free Coordination Of Multiple Mobile Robots

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Abstract -- This paper describes a technique for coordinating the decentralized planned trajectories of multiple mobile robots to avoid collisions and deadlocks between them. Robots exchange information about their planned trajectories whenever distance between the two robots drop below a certain value in order to determine whether they are going to collide. If robots detect collision, they monitor their movements. This paper also presents the problem of path planning for multiple mobile robots. It presents various approaches to coordinate the movements of the mobile robots in their environment.

1 . INTRODUCTION

Whenever multiple robots must operate in close proximity to each other, the potential for collision must be taken into account in specifying the robot trajectories. Goal is to allow the motions of each robot to be planned nearly independently and to allow the execution of the path segments to be asynchronous. That is,

- (1). Coordinating two robot so as to avoid collisions between them;
- (2). Guarantee the trajectories will reach their goals

V.J.Lumelsky and K.R.Harinarayan have

presented in their paper an approach for decentralized real-time motion planning for multiple mobile robots operating in a common 2-dimensional environment with unknown stationary obstacles. A robot can see (sense) the surrounding objects. It knows its current and its target's position, is able to distinguish a robot from an obstacle, and can assess the instantaneous motion of another robot. Other than this, a robot has no knowledge about the scene or of the paths and objectives of other robots. There is no mutual communication among the robots; no constraints are imposed on the paths or shapes of robots and obstacles.

Two approaches to motion planning in multi-agent systems are the **centralized** and **decentralized** (distributed) approach. In centralized motion planning, a central planner designs the motion plan for all robots based on full knowledge about the environment. Only after the complete paths have been computed, the actual motion takes place. The approach fits better purely computational problems rather than tasks that rely on real-time feedback control. Its obvious advantage is its conceptual simplicity: since everything is known, anything can be computed, including the optimal (shortest, smoothest etc.) trajectories for all agents. On the other hand, it has computational bottlenecks. The amount of computations quickly grows with the number of robots, and is likely to become clumsy in a task with 4-6 robots. Since planning

is done off-line, complete recalculation of paths is required if one of the robots' objectives are altered or if the environment changes.

Decentralized control has two obvious advantages:

- (i) It breaks the computational bottleneck of centralized control; in principle, computational complexity of a decentralized system can be made independent of the number of robots in it.
- (ii) It is basically more stable and robust: it can tolerate changes and uncertainly; a failure of one or few robots does not kill the whole system.

On the negative side, the decentralized control is inherently incapable of delivering optimal performance: since at any moment each robot is lacking some information, optimality is ruled out. Instead, a reasonable, acceptable performance is sought.

Most of the literature on multiple robot motion planning is devoted to the centralized approach.

Figure 1: Each robot in the system consists of three layers. The task of the trajectory planning layer is to plan a trajectory for a certain robot, the trajectory coordination layer is responsible for coordinating the independently planned trajectories, and the trajectory execution layer moves the robot along its trajectory.

2. DEADLOCK AVOIDANCE

Deadlock between two robots can be avoided if the distance between two robots is kept larger than a certain distance, they are considered to be safe, i.e. not facing a possible conflicts in the near future. Each robot evaluates position information received from other robots to determine its distance to them. When the position evaluation of a robot determines that its

distance to another robot might be less than safe distance, it instantiates a coordination link to the other robot. The coordination link is only removed after the distance of the robots is safe again. Since for the maintenance of the coordination links communication is needed.

Coordinating the movements of two robots along their trajectories to avoid collision, is the task of coordination link. A robot and a coordination link interacts in a simple way. A robot takes permission of the link to move on or not. A robot has to ask each of its coordination links for permission before it is allowed to give the next segment of its trajectory to its trajectory execution layer.

To establish a coordination link between two robots, one robot is elected planner and the other robot becomes partner. After the planner is elected, he requests the trajectory segments from his partner. Based on his own and the partners trajectory, the planner determines a schedule for the two robots. The schedule consists of the following entries: both robots are allowed to move, only the planner is allowed to move, and only the partner is allowed to move. Using the schedule, the planner then gives permissions to himself and his partner. Initially, task-completion-diagram(TCD) is constructed as shown in figure 1. The trajectory segments of the planner are shown on the horizontal axis and the segments of partner are shown on vertical axis

A coordination link is only used to coordinate the movement of two robots. The coordination of more than two robots results from the fact that a robot can have more than one coordination link. Since a robot needs the permission from all its coordination links before it is allowed to move on, the coordination links connect all the involved robots in a global coordination structure. This global coordination structure, however, can contain deadlocks, some robots mutually wait for each other which have to be detected and resolved.

Figure 2: A task-completion-diagram (TCD) with collision regions and an execution path from the lower left to the upper right corner.

3. DEADLOCK DETECTION

If a coordination link does not give the permission to robot to move on, deadlocks occurs. A coordination link does not allow a robot to process next trajectory segment. This occurs when the robot has to wait until the other robot has completed some of its trajectory segments. Whenever a robot is forced to wait for another one, a deadlock detection is initiated.

This can be shown by a directed graph. The case in which one robot has to wait for another can be seen as a directed edge from the waiting robot to the other robot in a graph in which every robot is represented by a graph node. Such a graph is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: A directed graph showing deadlocks among robots.

The nodes of the graph shown in this figure correspond to robots and a directed edge between two nodes is indicating that one robot is waiting for another one. The node from which an edge is originating corresponds to the waiting robot. Here, for example, robot 9 has to wait for robot 0. The case in which the construction of the execution path fails and in which none of the two robots is given the permission to move on, is represented as two edges connecting the two robots and pointing in opposite directions. Figure 2 shows this for robot 4 and 6.

In the context of the graph, a deadlock among the robots exists if and only if the graph contains a circle. Therefore deadlock detection means to detect a circle in the graph. Since this is a common problem in distributed deadlock detection, a lot of algorithms for that purpose have been developed. An algorithm proposed by [10], which only requires that each robot knows its outgoing edges to detect deadlocks. The algorithm works as follows: When a new directed edge is established the robot from which the edge originates initiates a new *probe* message and sends it along the edge. Whenever a robot receives a *probe* message it forwards the *probe* message along all its outgoing edges. The forwarded *probe* message contains the id of the visited robot so that deadlock cycles can be identified. If a robot receives a *probe* message which itself has initiated, it knows that the *probe* must have been forwarded along a circle and therefore detects a deadlock.

A disadvantage of this algorithm is that it is possible that more than one robot detect the same deadlock, e.g. if two robots initiate a deadlock detection for the same circle at the same time. [9] have proposed an improvement of the algorithm which ensures that each deadlock is only detected by exactly one robot. Using the improvement would not simplify the deadlock resolution strategy, since multiple deadlock resolutions which operate on the same edges can also occur if the graph contains multiple cycles which have nodes and edges in common.

The algorithm described above ensures that each deadlock is detected by at least one robot. It is however possible that phantom deadlocks are detected. This means, that a deadlock is detected which has already been resolved. This can happen if the deadlock has edges in common with another deadlock and if the deadlock resolution of the other deadlock modifies these edges. The deadlock resolution strategy is able to cope with such phantom deadlocks.

4. DEADLOCK RESOLUTION

A deadlock resolution, which is initiated by the robot detecting a deadlock, works by sending messages along the deadlock circle. Whenever it is not possible to forward a message along the circle, this indicates a phantom deadlock and the deadlock resolution terminates. A deadlock resolution comprises two steps. Initially an attempt is made to change the direction of one edge in the circle, since this would destroy the circle and therefore resolve the deadlock. If no edge direction can be changed, robots are chosen and asked to plan alternative trajectories.

If none of the two steps succeeds, which is considered to be very unlikely for real applications, all robots blocked by the deadlock are informed. These robots then do not participate any more in any deadlock detection or deadlock resolution process.

4.1 Planning of Alternative Trajectories

If no schedule which avoids the deadlock can be found for the robots, i.e. it is not possible to resolve a deadlock by changing an edge direction, it is necessary to plan alternative trajectories for one or more robots. The replanning has to be done in a controlled manner. It should be avoided that all robots plan alternative trajectories at the same time. The algorithm provided here tries to keep the number of robots which are forced to plan alternative trajectories low. It comprises two steps which are iterated until the deadlock is resolved or until it is determined that the deadlock cannot be resolved by asking individual robots to plan alternative trajectories. The latter case is considered to be very unlikely for real applications and depends solely on the abilities of the trajectory planning layer and the properties of the environment. The first step is to send a *replan* message around the circle, just as it is done with the *changemessage*. If a robot receives a *replan* message it asks its trajectory planning layer to plan an alternative trajectory. The robot can inform its trajectory planning layer about the positions of other robots surrounding it, i.e. other robots to which it has a coordination link, to obtain better results. After a robot was able to plan an alternative trajectory, all its outgoing edges are removed. Since this breaks the circle, the deadlock is resolved and the *replan* message can be discarded. If a robot receives a *replan* message which itself has

initiated, it knows that none of the robots in the circle is able to plan an alternative trajectory.

A robot is considered to be affected if it is part of the circle or if it is attached to the circle by an outgoing edge, either directly or transitive. Figure 6 shows a deadlock circle of the robots 1,2, and 3, and a number of other affected robots. The idea of the second step now is to check Criteria 6.1 and to ask affected robots which are not part of the circle to plan alternative trajectories. Criteria 6.1 is used to stop the iteration of the two steps in hopeless cases. The affected robots which are not part of the circle are asked to plan alternative trajectories in order to free as much robots as possible from the deadlock. During the second step a *free* message is sent to all affected robots. This is done by on the one hand sending the *free* message around the circle and on the other hand allowing the *free* message to leave the circle and traverse the affected robots in a depth-first way using incoming edges.

5. PATH PLANNING:

In this paper we consider the problem of motion planning for multiple mobile robots. the solutions known for single robot systems cannot directly be transferred to multi-robot systems. For example, [4] Decoupled planners determine the paths of the individual robots independently and then employ different strategies to resolve possible collisions. According to that, decoupled techniques are incomplete, i.e. they may fail to find a solution even if there is one. [5] applies potential field techniques in the configuration time-space to resolve conflicts. All these techniques assign priorities to the individual robots and compute the paths in decreasing order starting with the robot with highest priority. Whenever a path is planned, these approaches try to resolve the conflicts with the previously determined paths. In this context, an important question is how to assign the priorities to the individual robots. According to [6] higher priority is assigned to robots which can move on a straight line from the starting point to its target location. The approach described in [7] does not apply a priority scheme. Instead, it uses sets of alternative paths for the individual robots and determines a solution by applying heuristics to pick appropriate paths from the different sets. The path coordination method with decentralized planning is described in [2]. This method determines the paths of the individual robots

independently and then applies scheduling techniques to deal with possible collision. This technique keeps the robots on their individual paths and let the robots stop, move forward, or even move backward on their trajectories in order to avoid collisions. Although the coordination method was initially designed for two robots only, [8] can be extended to coordinate more than two robots.

In planning techniques described above, the environment is completely known and that it does not change during the operation of the robots.

The robots perform all actions with certainty. In reality in the populated environments these assumptions are generally violated, since the robots have to use their sensors to react to possible changes of the environment and to unexpected obstacles. Therefore, the robots often deviate from their previously planned paths.)

The method described by Maren Bennewitz Wolfram Burgard is a decentralized and prioritized approach to coordinated path-planning for multiple robots. It incorporates different types of uncertainty into the planning process. First, it computes the path of a robot by trading off the length of the trajectory and the distance to obstacles. The actions of the robots are assumed to be non-deterministic.

This approach plans the paths for the individual robots independently. If a conflict between the paths of two robots is detected it uses a priority scheme to re-plan the path of the robot with lower priority in its configuration timespace. Thereby it considers the constraints imposed by the robots with higher priority. This approach uses occupancy grid maps to plan the motions of the robots using \square _ . Simultaneously it trades off the length of the trajectory and the distance to objects in the environment. It furthermore uses a probabilistic model to integrate possible deviations of the robots from their planned paths into the planning process. Therefore, the resulting trajectories are robust even in situations in which the actual trajectories of the robots differ from the pre-planned paths.

6. CONCLUSION:

In this paper we described a decentralized approach for collision avoidance, deadlock detection, and deadlock resolution among multiple mobile robots which follow independently planned trajectories. Deadlocks in the global coordination, which cannot be avoided when only local coordination is used, are reliably detected. The deadlocks are resolved by

changing the direction of coordination links and asking robots to plan alternative trajectories. The only deadlocks which cannot be resolved are those where the trajectory planning layers of the involved robots are not able to plan alternative trajectories.

This, however, depends solely on the abilities of the trajectory planning layer and the properties of the environment. The strict separation of trajectory planning and collision avoidance/deadlock handling makes it possible to use a lot of different trajectory planners with our system. The only restriction is, that they should be able to plan alternative trajectories. There are no other special assumptions about the environment or the application made.

This approach is very suitable to coordinate a number of independently moving robots through local inter robot communication in a lot of applications. For further work, we consider it interesting to investigate different strategies for the construction of the execution paths of the TCDs. Furthermore, different strategies for the collision avoidance could be evaluated.

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